

Research

A Study on the Novellas reflecting the Era(Novellas by Myanmar Chinese Writer Xu)

刘志美(Nan San Htwe) 湖北大学, 武汉, 中国

Chinese Department, Mandalay University of Foreign Languages

Accepted: 15 November, 2020 ; *Online:* 21 November, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4284113>

Abstract: *The aim of this research is to highlight the fact that the reflection of economic and social conditions of an era can be found in the work of a Chinese writer who was in a foreign country. Based on the nature of the novellas, novellas by the writer Xu were used as the materials of the study. The nature of the novellas and their reflections on the era were presented in the study. Important subject matters of the novellas and their reflections on the different eras were highlighted in this research.*

Keywords: *human's nature, human's character, reflection, era.*

Introduction

Modern novellas usually depict the nature of human beings, their emotions and actions. The goodwill of the writer can be seen in modern novellas since unseemly matters are illustrated in them. The subject matters of the novellas change throughout the different eras. The themes of the modern novellas differ depending on the feeling of the writers. The story, the characters, modern view and modern thought highlighted in novellas are studied depending on the subject matter, event and emotion.

Materials and methods

The Nature of Novellas

Literary works which include personal anecdotes can draw the readers' attention. Both the novella and the novel are popular nowadays.

Although the novellas seem to be narrow in area, they have deep meanings. In University Knowledge Bank Journal, Professor U Tin Shwe stated that novellas are short and concise

compositions which can well illustrate a particular event. The novella is a literary genre which was developed in Western countries in the 19th century. Edgar Allan Poe is considered as the inventor of novellas. Edgar Allan Poe is regarded as the first one who defined the structures modern novellas. According to him,

“Since there is only one emotion in a novella, the characters, the plot, time and situation should be developed together to reveal the emotion. Moreover, the novella only focus on a single plotline and it should be in a length that can be read in a single day.

According to Myanmar Dictionary,

“A novella is a kind of literary genre which focuses on one or more characters and the writer composes the event and the subject matter in an interesting way”. (Myanmar Language Commissions, 1991, 164)

The Reflection of Era in a Novella

“Hu Ke De Wu Nai” is a novella which is included in the book “Ximeng de gu shi (the collection of novellas)” published by Sichuan Literature and Art Publishing House in 2013. Those novellas were written in the period which needed economic and social stability and development, so they led to the society from human character and nature. In modern novellas, writer Xu described migration to foreign countries because of instability, and the difficulties and struggles facing while running business. The novella highlighted the description of the period and it was the mirror of the era. Therefore, the social and economic conditions of the society can be found in the novellas of Myanmar Chinese writer Xu.

Aim

Writer Xu clearly stated the theme of his novella. He depicted the social conditions of Chinese people who moved to other countries. The main aim of the novella is to present the social difficulties.

Plot

The story was about an employee who did not have legal residency in Makao and he was forced to work without pay.

Characters

There were two main characters in that novella. The first one is “Hu Ke” who lived and worked in Makao illegally while the second one was the selfish boss who did not pay the employees for their work.

Social Background

People have different characters and different nature; some are good whereas some are evil. Some people are overwhelmed by greed, anger and ignorance while some can overcome them. Social descriptions of people in samsara (cycle of rebirths) are illustrated in the novella of Xu. In the novella, the factory owner represents evil people who only look for self-interest. Under the name of the savior, such kinds of people look for self-interest in a wrong way. “Hu Ke” had a safe and sound place in a highly populated building located in the northern part of Makao. He spent about half of a year in that small room, which is used as a bedroom and also a working place. The machine with the length of 1 meter is the only thing that could make him please. He thanks his boss for letting him, a man without legal residency, in that small place.

The writer developed the theme of the novella through the actions of the characters and their conversations. He skillfully illustrated the self-centered nature of the boss and the society. Writer Xu described the subject matter, the facts and the aim of the novella by highlighting the society. In the novella “Hu Ke’s Impatience”, writers described the difficulties of illegal employees and he also highlighted the self-centered society in business world.

Discussion

The novella is a kind of literary genre which was first developed in late 19th century. They are based on the incidents in real life, so they show human nature and character. The novella of writer Xu is not just an ordinary one; it points out unseemly situation in that period. It compares the lives of employees struggling to survive in a foreign country and those of the selfish employers who took advantages from the employees. It describes the ego of the people in business world. Therefore, that novella is not just a descriptive writing; it also point out and criticize the situations happening in that period. It also describes the nature of self-centered men who thought that they could do everything if they have power, and the ignorance of uneducated people. It highlights the

nature of egocentric people who never hesitate to do evil deeds for their interest. In the novella “Hu Ke’s Impatience”, Hu Ke got into trouble when he moved to a foreign country as an illegal resident to work. Despite the trouble, he worked hard in order to please the boss and get the remaining salary, yet he was arrested. The writer Xu described the life of an illegal resident in a sympathetic way. The novella highlights the necessity of knowledge and consciousness.

“Although he had to work overtime, he got one-fourth of the salary of a legal worker.”

“He was excited when he got the first salary. After paying the rent, he had to live on a small amount of money. Later, the owner did not pay the salary on time by giving the excuse of final difficulty”.

Later, according to the neighbors’ words, Hu Ke came to know that the boss had already bought a new car and house, and he saw his boss appearing in a TV programme. Although Hu Ke did not get the salary for eight months, he did not know the place where he could report about his problem. All he could do was to try to finish the work on time and hope that the boss would sympathize him.”

The writer vividly described the employer as a selfish, unsympathetic man who used the power to take advantage from others. The boss employed illegal residents for his self-interest: to buy new car, to own new house etc. The characters of the boss were described through the conversations between the employees. The opinion of the boss represented the opinion of the employers in that period. He represented people who prioritized their own self-interest. That description highlighted self-centered society in business world.

The description “Although Hu Ke could go back to his native town after living thriftily for 2 years, the current problem is that the boss asks him to work overtime and the salary is just one-fourth of a legal employee” illustrates the lives of workers who worked hard to return to their native towns and settle down. The writer described the nature of most illegal residents who wanted to settle down in their native towns.

Conclusion

Novella is a literary work which describes the nature and character of human beings and the events in real life. The novella “Hu Ke’s Impatience” reflects the common situation happening

between the employer and the employees. In his work, writer Xu depicted the situations of the society in that period.

References

1. Tin Shwe, U. (Professor). Myanmar Novellas around 1920s. Takkatho Pinyar Padaythar Sarsaung, Vol.13, No.6, Yangon Ahtettan Pinyar Padaythar Sarsaung, Vol.13, No.6, Yangon Ahtettan Pinyar Department.
2. Guy E. Smith, American Literature, P.265.
3. Myanmar Language Commissions, 1991, Myanmar Dictionary, Yangon, Myanmar Language Department.
4. Xu Jun Quan, Ximeng de gushi, Chengdu, Sichuan wenyi chubenshe, 2013.2.

Nan San Htwe (Liu Zhi Mei),born in 20th November,1973 get the first B.A,Chemistry(Mandalay University) in 30th October,1999 and then completed M.A. Chinese(Mandalay University of Foreign Languages) in 12th January,2016.Mini-novels are the ones that can acknowledge people and make them relax. As I am a person who approach Chinese Language and culture, this mini-novels help me

a lot in learning. Among them, short novels written by Myanmar-born Chinese are the best for me and therefore, I do this research and I believe this will help many people, who are learning Chinese Language ,to get the ideas what to read to be more proficient.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

